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ETHICAL DECISIONS and MIDWIFERY APPROACHES in THE PRENATAL DIAGNOSIS PROCESS

PRENATAL TANI SÜRECİNDE ETİK KARARLAR ve EBELİK YAKLAŞIMLARI

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ABSTRACT

With the rapid advancement of technology and the widespread use of prenatal diagnostic methods, families and healthcare professionals are faced with critical decisions regarding the detection of fetal abnormalities, including those in the early stages of pregnancy. In this context, midwives, who encounter pregnant women more frequently than other health professionals during the prenatal period, often witness ethical issues in the prenatal diagnosis process. Routine prenatal care practices are not limited to technical procedures or technological requirements; they also involve cultural determinants related to disability, eugenics, welfare, and prevention. The effectiveness of midwives in this process helps to maintain the emotional and mental well-being of couples, improve maternal and neonatal outcomes, and increase the quality of care. At the same time, midwives' individual and ethics-focused approach helps pregnant women make decisions that align with their beliefs and cultural values during the decision-making process by accelerating their compliance with the results of screening and diagnostic tests. At this point, it is crucial for midwives to provide support services that respect the individual's decision-making process, informed consent, and transcultural approaches in managing existing ethical dilemmas. The aim of this review is to examine ethical issues arising during the prenatal diagnosis process, their impact on decision-making, and the role of midwives, emphasizing the importance of a midwifery approach that focuses on women.

Keywords: Ethics, ethical dilemma, midwifery, prenatal diagnosis,

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ÖZET

Gün geçtikçe hızla ilerleyen teknoloji ile beraber prenatal tanı yöntemlerinin yaygın olarak kullanımı, erken gebelik dönemleri de dahil olmak üzere fetusa ait anomalilerin saptanmasında hem ailelerin hem de bu alanda görevli sağlık profesyonellerinin kritik kararlarla karşı karşıya kalmasına sebep olmaktadır. Bu bağlamda diğer sağlık profesyonellerine göre prenatal dönemde gebelerle daha sık karşılaşılan ebeler, prenatal tanılama sürecindeki etik konulara sıklıkla şahit olmaktadır. Prenatal bakımla alakalı rutin uygulamalar yalnızca teknik birtakım uygulamalar ya da teknolojik zorunlulukları kapsamamakta aynı zamanda engellilik, öjeni, refah ve önleme ile alakalı görüşlerin de kültürel belirleyicilerinin olduğu bir konu olarak karşımıza çıkmaktadır. Ebelerin bu süreçteki etkinliği, çiftlerin duygusal ve ruhsal iyilik hallerini korumaya yardımcı olmakta, maternal ve neonatal sonuçları iyileştirmekte ve bakımın kalitesini arttırabilmektedir. Aynı zamanda ebelerin bireysel ve etik odaklı yaklaşımı, gebelerin tarama ve tanı testlerinin sonuçlarına uyumunu hızlandırarak tercih aşamasında, gebe kadınların inanç ve kültürel değerleri ile örtüşen kararlar almasında yardımcı olmaktadır. Bu noktada ebelerin, mevcut etik ikilemlerin yönetiminde bireyin karar alma sürecine saygı duyma, aydınlatılmış onam, transkültürel yaklaşım gibi konuları içerisinde barındıran bir destek hizmeti sunmaları oldukça önemlidir. Bu derlemenin amacı, prenatal dönemde tanı sürecinde ortaya çıkan etik problemler, bu problemlerin karar alma üzerindeki etkileri ile ebelerin rollerini incelemek, kadını merkeze alan bir ebelik yaklaşımının önemine vurgu yapmaktır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Etik, etik ikilemler, ebelik, prenatal tanı.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid advancement of technology, the widespread use of prenatal diagnostic methods has led to families and healthcare professionals having to make critical decisions regarding the detection of fetal abnormalities, including those in early pregnancy. Prenatal diagnostic tests, which include both non-invasive and invasive diagnostic methods, provide important data regarding fetal health (Ceylan Yorulmaz et al.,2024).Therefore, ethical dilemmas arising from certain adverse conditions detected by prenatal diagnostic methods bring to the fore issues such as newborn rights, the right to life of persons with disabilities, social acceptance, and termination of pregnancy (Barış & İlkılıç, 2018).Especially in recent years, with the introduction of non-invasive prenatal testing (NIPT), existing ethical debates have intensified. The results of tests used to detect different genetic variants early in the prenatal period are decisive in families' decision-making, making this an important issue that needs to be addressed (Sánchez Marín & García González,2023).Although these tests can detect many preventable conditions in the early stages of pregnancy, they also have some disadvantages. The uncertainty of the clinical picture that develops based on the test results and the controversial accuracy rates are among these disadvantages. For example, in the dual screening test, one of the first-trimester screening tests, the probability of detecting trisomy 21 ranges from 82% to 87%, while the disease detection rates of quadruple screening tests can vary between 80% and 94%. These rates may vary depending on the laboratory. Therefore, it is essential to provide couples with a detailed explanation of what the results of screening and diagnostic tests mean and the differences between screening and diagnostic tests (Doğan &

Akdöner,2022).In this context, midwives, who encounter pregnant women more frequently than other health professionals during the prenatal period, often witness ethical issues in the prenatal diagnosis process. At this point, it is crucial for midwives to provide a support service that encompasses issues such as respecting the individual's decision-making process, informed consent, and a transcultural approach in managing existing ethical dilemmas (Gadsbøll at al.,2020; Harris,2018).The purpose of this review is to examine the ethical problems that arise during the prenatal diagnosis process, their effects on decision-making, and the roles of midwives, emphasizing the importance of a midwifery approach that centers on women.

2. PRENATAL DIAGNOSIS PROCESS

During pregnancy, a series of screening and diagnostic tests are performed to detect genetic, chromosomal, or structural abnormalities in the fetus at an early stage, which is referred to as the prenatal diagnosis process. Prenatal screening tests indicate the risk ratio of a disease occurring, while prenatal diagnostic tests provide definitive results on whether a disease is present or not (Doğan&Akdöner,2022). These screening and diagnostic tests include ultrasound, dual screening, triple screening, and quadruple screening tests based on maternal serum markers, non-invasive prenatal screening tests (NIPT) that also evaluate genomes carrying sex chromosomes, amniocentesis, chorionic villus sampling (Doğan&Akdöner,2022;Sağol&Taşdemir,2018).In cases of sporadic pregnancy loss, which is a common condition among women of childbearing age, preimplantation genetic diagnosis and screening tests may also be recommended. These diagnostic and screening tests are performed to predict obstetric outcomes, assess fetal health, and identify conditions that threaten the life of the fetus and possible risks at an early stage (Gadsbøll at al.,2020).Screening and diagnostic tests performed during the prenatal period can provide data on the presence of chromosomal disorders such as Down syndrome, neural tube defects, genetically transmitted single-gene disorders, and other structural anomalies (Doğan&Akdöner,2022).Pregnant women can be referred for further diagnosis if a risk is identified as a result of screening tests, and early intervention can improve neonatal health outcomes (Dukhovny&Norton;2018).However, the results of prenatal screening and diagnostic tests do not always indicate good fetal health; they can also reveal negative fetal outcomes that cannot be intervened upon. In a study conducted in our country in 2022, it was found that as the number of maternal serum markers with abnormal results increased in screening tests performed in the first and second trimesters, or as the relevant markers approached their maximum abnormal level, the likelihood of poor obstetric outcomes increased (Cellek&Çağlar;2022).On the other hand, invasive prenatal diagnostic tests such as amniocentesis and chorionic villus sampling carry certain risks. For example, in a systematic review and meta-analysis published in 2023, indications for late amniocentesis performed after the 24th week of pregnancy include suspicious ultrasound findings, fetal growth restriction, advanced maternal age, suspected fetal infection, abnormal serum marker findings, maternal request, and a history of genetic disease. The same study also noted that after the 24th week of pregnancy include preterm birth within one week following amniocentesis, premature membrane rupture, chorioamnionitis, placental abruption, intrauterine fetal death, and pregnancy loss, with the incidence varying according to gestational age (Nassr et al.,2023).Therefore, the risks specific to the tests performed during the prenatal diagnosis

process and the detection of abnormal conditions in the test results may lead to the need to make critical decisions regarding the continuation or termination of the pregnancy (Hayırlıdağ,2022).

3. PROFESSIONAL ETHICS and MIDWIFERY

The concept of ethics, which has a long history worldwide, refers to the principles that determine the behavior of individuals and societies and evaluate whether something is good or bad. Ethics has been a topic of debate among various circles, from scientists to religious scholars, throughout history. Medical ethics has also been part of these debates, which have shed light on the establishment of ethical codes in medical practice (Markose,Krishnan,&Ramesh;2016).Health ethics principles, which remain important today, are described by the World Health Organization (WHO) as one of the essential elements for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (Worldh Helath Organization; retrieved June 1,2025).In this context, midwives providing healthcare and counseling services specifically to women, families, and communities, and playing a leading role in protecting maternal and child health, is a very important issue in the professional ethics of midwifery. Indeed, the International Confederation of Midwives (ICM) has developed and published professional ethical rules for midwifery. The International Confederation of Midwives International Code of Ethics for Midwives contains ethical codes regarding midwifery relationships, midwifery practices, professional responsibilities, and the advancement of midwifery knowledge and practice. The ICM International Midwifery Code of Ethics emphasizes the importance of recognizing, defending, and respecting women's human rights (International Confederation of Midwives; retrieved June 1,2025).It also encourages ethical self-regulation in midwifery practice, strengthens professional identity, protects caregivers and care recipients, and draws attention to professional maturity (Foster,Lasser,&Bartlett; 2015). Professional ethics in midwifery can be linked to fundamental principles such as women's autonomy, respectful birth care, and women's rights related to childbirth (Ceylan Yorulmaz et al.,2024).. These ethical foundations, which must be established from the outset of midwifery education, serve as an effective tool for midwives to understand and manage ethical issues through transparent information sharing and the provision of care within an ethical framework (Eagen-Torkko & Levi, 2020;Dönmez, Yeyğel,&Kılınç,2022).Informed consent, privacy, ethical decision-making, and ethical sensitivity are becoming increasingly important issues (MacLellan,2014;Kurnaz&Çoban,2025).

3.1. Ethics in the Prenatal Diagnosis Process

During the prenatal period, issues such as termination of pregnancy, fetal reduction, management in cases of sudden maternal brain death, and sex selection often give rise to ethical dilemmas (Eker&Şahin,2018). These ethical dilemmas may arise in situations that conflict with religious beliefs and social values. Routine practices related to prenatal care are not merely technical procedures or technological necessities; they also involve cultural determinants related to disability, eugenics, welfare, and prevention (Rehmann-Sutter,Timmermans,&Raz;2023). For example, in a study conducted in our country in 2025 with Turkish pregnant women, 58.7% of pregnant women chose to continue their pregnancy after being diagnosed with anencephaly, while 92.4% chose to continue their pregnancy after

being diagnosed with Down syndrome. The same study also revealed that these preferences are influenced by cultural and religious factors, as well as feelings of guilt, the short life expectancy of the baby, and concerns about its future life (Babadağlı,Aydın,&Ersoy;2025).The selection of fetuses based on gender in different cultures raises ethical debates, particularly in relation to NIPT testing, while the termination of pregnancies in cases of anomalies is also debated from an ethical perspective (Atar&Şahinoğlu,2023;Vanstone et al.,2014). Other ethical debates related to NIPT include its limited accessibility and high cost, as well as false positive results leading to unnecessary invasive diagnostic tests. Furthermore, its limited accessibility conflicts with the principle of justice within general professional ethical principles (Vanstone et al.,2014;Esen,Gerçek,&Uyar Hazar,2022). Results of a cross-sectional study conducted in the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires, Argentina; shows that congenital anomalies affecting the nervous system are more commonly detected in public health institutions through prenatal screening, while Down syndrome is more commonly detected in private health institutions. This difference is attributed to the fact that the advantaged population has greater access to prenatal diagnosis and, consequently, more abortions (Brun et al.,2024). Another study indicates that pregnant women living in socioeconomically disadvantaged areas of the Netherlands are less likely to undergo noninvasive prenatal screening tests (Rehmann-Sutter,Timmermans,&Raz;2023). On the other hand, issues such as the fact that information obtained from screening tests performed in the early stages of pregnancy will increase elective termination of pregnancy, that negative test results will adversely affect reproductive autonomy, and that families will not be able to make informed choices about whether to undergo testing if they are not adequately informed, also arise as ethical issues in the prenatal diagnosis process (Zaami et al,2021).Another ethical issue that has arisen in relation to screening and diagnostic tests performed during the prenatal period is whether or not to report the many different variants that have been identified as a result of advancing technology, which may or may not be significant .The preference for abortion in cases of anomalies detected by prenatal screening and diagnostic tests raises ethical debates regarding the right to life, newborn rights, and disability rights. However, from the parents' perspective, the psychological, social, and physical challenges of caring for a child with disabilities also make the decision-making process quite difficult in an ethical context (Türkçapar&Büken,2024)..False positive or negative results from screening tests are another issue that complicates the ethical decision-making process (Esen,Gerçek,&Uyar Hazar,2022). Indeed, due to false negative results, many couples may opt for abortion, or even if they do not decide to have an abortion, they may experience various emotional problems, primarily anxiety, throughout their pregnancy. In addition, ethicists consider the mandatory nature of some prenatal screening and diagnostic tests to be controversial in the context of the principle of autonomy (Hayırlıdağ,2022). In this context, the literature states that valid criteria must be determined by conducting studies that include routine ethics and distinctions between the levels and forms of routines in order to make prenatal screening and diagnostic tests routine (Rehmann-Sutter,Timmermans,&Raz;2023).

3.2. Ethical Issues and Midwifery Approaches in the Prenatal Diagnosis Process

The ethical decision-making process is one of the processes that may be encountered during the prenatal period. When managing this process, it is extremely important to demonstrate a correct and fair approach based on general ethical principles and models such as

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the ethical codes published by the ICM for midwives. These basic principles include respect for autonomy, non-maleficence, beneficence, and justice (Foster,Lasser,&Bartlett; 2015). The care model to be implemented by midwives, based on ethical principles in the prenatal diagnosis process, should encourage the expectant mother and family to make informed and autonomous decisions regarding fetal health, management of the pregnancy, and possible outcomes (Gadsbøll at al.,2020). In this context, midwives have roles in informing pregnant women, supporting the natural process, guiding them toward informed decision-making, and providing guidance within their authority regarding the meaning of the tests and their possible outcomes, taking into account the needs of pregnant women during the prenatal screening and diagnostic testing process(Kurul&Mecdi Kaydırak;2022; Sađol&Taşdemir,2018). Families encounter unusual procedures, genetic testing, and unknown results during the prenatal diagnosis process, which can lead to ineffective coping, spiritual issues, and concerns about the safety of the baby, accompanied by a lack of information. The effectiveness of midwives in this process helps to maintain the emotional and mental well-being of couples, improve maternal and neonatal outcomes, and increase the quality of care. At the same time, midwives' individual and ethics-focused approach helps pregnant women make decisions that align with their beliefs and cultural values during the decision-making process by accelerating their compliance with the results of screening and diagnostic tests (Dahl,Heinonen,&Bondas;2020).The decision-making process that takes place in response to negative prenatal diagnosis results involves careful consideration of the consequences of continuing the pregnancy. The information obtained as a result of the diagnosis, the current situation of the couple, and their future expectations must also be included in this assessment. Indeed, the personal values, beliefs, and religious views of the couple will influence the decision they make during this period (American Collage of Obstetricians and Gynecologists,2021). A study conducted in our country also emphasizes that personal values are influential in the decision-making process regarding the continuation or termination of pregnancy after diagnosis, and that midwives should support couples in such decision-making processes with ethical sensitivity (Yılmaz&Güven;2021).During the conflict between fetal autonomy and parental autonomy, midwives must help couples access accurate information. Here, accurate information includes detailed and evidence-based explanations of what diagnostic methods mean, what the possible outcomes are, and what the options are. In order for couples to make autonomous decisions during the prenatal diagnostic process, all their questions must be answered patiently (International Confederation of Midwife; retrieved June 1,2025). In addition, it is recommended that midwives provide medical information in stages, taking into account the values of the couple when providing counseling on prenatal diagnosis. In this context, a three-stage counseling model is proposed, in which the first stage involves assessing whether the couple wishes to receive information about the genetic status of the fetus, the second stage involves ensuring that prospective parents make a decision after being informed and then obtaining informed consent, and the third stage involves supporting them in continuing or terminating the pregnancy based on the test results (Vanstone at al.,2014). In the informed choice process, the competence of decision-makers, the selection of the most appropriate alternative from among the available options, the provision of information about the alternatives and the action decided upon, and ensuring that the decision-making process is free from coercion are important points to consider. It is also very important for midwives to take these criteria into account when providing information and planning care (Zielinski et

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al.,2020). Another ethical debate related to prenatal screening and diagnostic tests is that counseling couples in accordance with the principle of non-maleficence in order to prevent the risk of eugenics is an ethical approach. Health professionals and midwives working in this field should evaluate each case individually in the event of a conflict of principles and provide counseling accordingly (Hayırlıdağ,2022) .

4. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The diagnostic process during the prenatal period is complex and raises ethical issues for both prospective parents and healthcare professionals. In particular, the possibility of detecting fetal anomalies in the very early stages of pregnancy necessitates critical decisions, while also bringing to the fore ethical principles such as respect for individual autonomy, informed consent, privacy, benefit-risk balance, and justice. In this process, midwives play a key role in helping families make more conscious and healthy choices from an ethical perspective, not only by providing care services but also by acting as advisors, guides, and supporters. During this period, midwives must demonstrate an approach that is not only based on technical skills but also equipped with a strong ethical awareness and empathy. In this context, in-service training that includes ethically controversial case presentations, the dissemination of a transcultural approach, awareness-raising activities, the development of guidelines on the subject, the promotion of research to identify the current situation, and multidisciplinary collaboration are of great importance for the empowerment of midwives.

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